

I have been asked by Dr. Javier Pérez-Barbería to provide comments on the quality and adequacy of his teaching project to apply for a senior position at the Department of Science and Agroforestry Technology and Genetics of University of Castilla/La Mancha under the Beatriz Galindo program.

I have worked on plant-herbivore interactions at physiological, individual and population levels. My work covers foraging behaviour, diet selection, the control of food intake, digestion and metabolism. I held positions of Reader in Ecology, Professor of Animal Ecology, Head of the School of Biological Sciences, and am now an Emeritus Professor at the University of Edinburgh. Having taught agriculture and ecology at various universities for about 40 years, I consider myself an appropriate reviewer to assess his teaching project.

The teaching project proposal appears to cover all themes described in the job description and also elaborates the most recent concepts concerning the ecosystem services provided by ruminants, their impact on biodiversity, landscapes and climate change. I found his approach a stimulating perspective on the study of ruminants for undergraduate and postgraduate students, including Graduate Diploma, Master and PhD, which fulfils the teaching areas the Department of Science and Agroforestry Technology and Genetics intends to cover.

I believe this teaching project will be a valuable asset for the teaching programme of the Department, and it constitutes an attractive option for the students who are interested in a multidisciplinary view of the societal and ecosystem role of ruminants and its sustainable management.

I know Javier to be a diligent and committed researcher, but especially as someone with an engaging personality who is an enthusiastic and amusing communicator. I consider

these qualities to be important attributes in a university teacher. His application has my full support.

Please feel free to contact me for further assistance (a.illius@ed.ac.uk)

Prof. Andrew Illius